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Editorial: Advancing literacy rights: teachers' roles in policy advocacy in multilingual settings

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Editorial on the Research Topic

[Advancing literacy rights: teachers' roles in policy advocacy in multilingual settings](#)

Although literacy continues to occupy a central place in global educational discourse, its meaning and implementation remain contested across diverse linguistic and cultural contexts. In multilingual and bilingual educational environments, literacy cannot be treated merely as the acquisition of reading and writing skills. Rather, it functions as a gateway to educational participation, social mobility, and civic engagement. As educational systems respond to demographic shifts, migration, and linguistic pluralism, the question of who will advocate for literacy rights becomes increasingly urgent. Within this complex landscape, teachers occupy a uniquely consequential position. They are not only implementers of policy but also interpreters, mediators, and, at times, critics of the literacy frameworks that shape classroom practice.

The concept of multiliteracies, first articulated by the New [London Group \(1996\)](#), expands the definition of literacy beyond traditional print-based models to encompass multimodal and culturally situated practices. Multiliteracies emphasize the integration of linguistic, visual, spatial, gestural, and digital modes of meaning-making within educational contexts ([Cope and Kalantzis, 2023](#)). At the same time, global discussions surrounding the Science of Reading continue to influence literacy policy by foregrounding phonics-based instruction and cognitive approaches to reading development. While these frameworks offer valuable insights into reading acquisition, they often fail to consider the realities of multilingual learners whose linguistic repertoires extend across multiple languages and cultural domains. In engaging with these tensions, this Research Topic speaks back to dominant interpretations of the Science of Reading—not in opposition, but in extension—highlighting the need to situate reading instruction within multilingual, culturally diverse, and policy-sensitive contexts, which these frameworks do not always fully account for. The resulting tension between standardized reading frameworks and context-sensitive literacy practices raises critical questions about equity, inclusion, and the role of teachers in advocating for literacy policies that recognize linguistic diversity.

The contributions to this Research Topic engage directly with these challenges by examining teacher agency, instructional realities, and policy possibilities in multilingual educational settings. Spanning contexts such as Ethiopia, Saudi Arabia, and the Philippines, along with broader international analyses of culturally and linguistically diverse classrooms, the articles collectively foreground the global dimensions of literacy advocacy. Together, they illuminate how teachers navigate institutional expectations, linguistic demands, and pedagogical responsibilities while advocating for more equitable literacy practices. These studies also demonstrate that literacy advocacy operates across multiple layers of educational experience, ranging from student perceptions and teacher self-efficacy to institutional policy and national reform initiatives.

One study in this Research Topic examines students' attitudes toward studying English as a major field of study within an Ethiopian university context. Drawing on data from remedial students, [Duresa et al.](#) identify a range of factors that discourage students from pursuing English language studies, including perceptions of the discipline as excessively difficult, limited awareness of career opportunities, and insufficient exposure to English learning in earlier stages of education. These findings highlight an often-overlooked dimension of literacy advocacy: the role of teachers in shaping students' academic aspirations and linguistic identities. At the same time, the Ethiopian case reflects a broader global tension. Despite the persistent positioning of English as a lingua franca in education, employment, and transnational communication, students' reluctance to engage with the language reveals a disconnect between global linguistic demands and local educational experiences. In this sense, this case serves as a signpost for similar challenges in multilingual contexts where the symbolic power of English does not always translate into meaningful access or sustained engagement. As such, the study underscores the importance of teacher guidance and advocacy in encouraging students to recognize the broader educational and professional value of language learning.

While student perceptions shape entry points into literacy-related fields, teachers' own beliefs about their instructional abilities significantly influence classroom practice. Addressing this dimension, [Peterson and Jensen](#) provide a systematic review of research on teacher self-efficacy in culturally and linguistically diverse classrooms. Their synthesis reveals that teachers who possess strong self-efficacy are more likely to adopt inclusive pedagogical strategies, demonstrate resilience in challenging instructional contexts, and maintain higher levels of professional well-being. Conversely, low levels of self-efficacy may contribute to teacher burnout and limited engagement with students from diverse linguistic backgrounds. Importantly, their review also identifies factors that shape teacher self-efficacy, including access to professional development, opportunities for intercultural engagement, and the availability of instructional resources. These findings reinforce the idea that effective literacy advocacy cannot be separated from the professional conditions under which teachers work.

Another contribution to this Research Topic shifts the focus to the higher education context by examining English-medium instruction (EMI) in STEM programs. [Abdel Latif and Alrashed](#)

investigate the English communication practices, self-perceived abilities, and linguistic needs of STEM lecturers at Saudi universities. Their findings reveal significant variation in lecturers' confidence in using English for instruction, with science lecturers reporting particularly high communication needs compared to their peers in engineering and information technology fields. The study also demonstrates a strong relationship between lecturers' perceived language competence and their classroom communication practices. These results highlight the critical importance of language support and professional development in contexts where English functions as the primary medium of instruction. Without adequate linguistic preparation, teachers may struggle to communicate complex disciplinary content effectively, potentially limiting students' access to knowledge. Thus, teacher advocacy in multilingual education must also encompass institutional efforts to support educators' language development.

The final article in this collection addresses literacy advocacy from a policy perspective by examining the persistent challenge of functional illiteracy in the Philippines. Drawing on national survey data, [Manuel et al.](#) propose the institutionalization of Multilingual Reading Interventionists (MRIs) in junior high schools as a strategic response to the country's literacy gap. Their policy brief highlights how socioeconomic inequality, linguistic diversity, and limited instructional support contribute to enduring literacy challenges. By introducing specialized reading professionals trained in regional languages and culturally responsive pedagogies, the proposed MRI framework seeks to strengthen existing literacy programs while addressing the specific needs of multilingual learners. The authors argue that institutionalizing these roles in the education system would not only enhance reading support but also reinforce teachers' ability to advocate for literacy rights in their schools and communities.

Taken together, the articles in this Research Topic demonstrate that literacy advocacy cannot be confined to a single dimension of educational practice. Instead, it emerges through the dynamic interplay of student attitudes, teacher beliefs, instructional competence, and policy innovation. Teachers stand at the intersection of these forces. They influence students' academic trajectories, shape classroom learning environments, and contribute to broader conversations about literacy policy and educational equity.

As educational systems continue to address the challenges of linguistic diversity and global mobility, the importance of teacher advocacy in advancing literacy rights will only intensify. Future research should therefore continue to explore how teachers can be empowered as policy actors, instructional innovators, and community advocates within multilingual educational settings. By recognizing teachers not only as implementers of policy, but as agents of educational transformation, scholars and policymakers alike can move closer to realizing a more inclusive vision of literacy education.

Ultimately, advancing literacy rights requires sustained collaboration among educators, researchers, and policymakers. The contributions presented in this Research Topic offer valuable insights into how such collaboration can unfold. More importantly, they remind us that literacy, in its fullest sense, is not simply a skill to be taught but a right to be defended.

Author contributions

AG: Conceptualization, Writing – original draft. JT: Writing – review & editing. MK: Writing – review & editing. AL: Writing – review & editing. CD: Writing – review & editing.

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